

Putting Context into Hypermedia MAS

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Abstract. In agent-oriented software engineering there is a recent emphasis on development of Hypermedia Multi-Agent System (HMAS). This approach seeks to align MAS engineering with the Web architecture, fostering the development of large-scale, open, dynamic, and enduring interactions of human and software agents alike. The scale and dynamics of the interactions require a method to organize the provisioning of information that informs and is *contextual* to the interactions. We present the design of a framework that addresses the management of context information, while aligning with and using engineering principles of HMAS and streaming of knowledge over the web. We detail the implementation of a first use-case for the framework: the enabling of dynamic, context-based access control to web resources in an HMAS environment, by means of technologies such as RDF stream processing, SHACL and SOLID Web Access Control.

Keywords: Hypermedia MAS · Web-of-Things · Context Management
· Context-Based Access Control · RDF Stream Processing · SHACL

1 Introduction

Hypermedia Multi-Agent Systems (HMAS [13]) is a novel class of MAS design which advocates for the alignment of MAS engineering with the web architecture to facilitate the development of large, open, dynamic, and long-lasting interaction systems. Central to this approach is the utilization of semantic hypermedia to facilitate interaction among diverse entities, including software agents, sensors, devices, services, and individuals.

An exemplar engineering framework [15] within the HMAS community suggests aligning the Agents and Artifacts (A&A) MAS development meta-model [25] with the Web-of-Things (WoT) W3C Thing Description (TD) specification [9]. The A&A model incorporates a distinct aspect for the programming of a MAS environment, involving the utilization of *artifacts* and their deployment across different *workspaces*. The artifacts serve to encapsulate the functionalities of digital services, sensors, or actuators, presenting their operations through observable properties, events, and actionable commands.

HMAS promotes design principles [15] that build up a strong support for *discoverability* of services on the web. These principles refer to aspects such as uniform representation of resources (e.g. in RDF), discovery through single points of entry

(exploiting the HATEOAS - Hypermedia as Engine of Application State - guideline of self-descriptive resources) and observability of resource affordances [15]. The latter point is put further into focus by the perspective of signifiers [32, 21] which are an abstraction providing a means for resources in an HMAS environment to signal and advertise their affordances to agents who are *able* and *interested* in exploiting them for their objectives.

Signifiers in particular, and agent interactions in an HMAS in general, are expected to be varied (e.g. in terms of complexity or agent and resource capabilities) and dynamic (e.g. in terms of duration or physical and logical agent mobility). This brings about the requirement to specify *the context* under which they can occur. Indeed, the signifier formalisation specifies a context element that contains the sum of conditions that *have to* characterize the situation of an agent in the HMAS environment, such that the currently desired affordance of a resource can be exploited [32].

However, the signifier formalism and the HMAS design principles do not provide suggestions or guidelines as to how the information and affordances about a resource in an HMAS can become *context* for an interaction, or how an agent can become aware and access such information in a principled manner. Put otherwise, an approach for *provisioning* of context information is currently not addressed by efforts to develop frameworks in support of HMAS environment engineering.

We therefore intend to provide a principled manner by which existing HMAS engineering frameworks (e.g. Yggdrasil [15]) can be extended with support for context information management. For the proposed context management extension we identify an important usage, namely the enabling of *context-based access control*, arguing that the the mobility of both human and software agents (e.g. physically or in terms of *roles* played in activities) requires a mechanism of authorization that exploits the dynamic context of the interactions, beyond a standard token based authentication. Importantly, elements of our proposal align with the vision of the RDF Stream Processing community [4], which looks to support dynamic interactions, such as those in an HMAS, by means of connecting streams of data over the web [17]. The contributions of this paper, as part of a framework that we call CASHMERE, are:

- (i) The description of a method to represent, store and manage context information in an HMAS platform adhering to the Agents&Artifacts paradigm. We argue that a context management service needs to be designed to provide indexing services (listing *how/where* context information provided by an HMAS resource can be accessed), as well as republishing services to forward context information on behalf of HMAS resources which are constrained.
- (ii) The design and implementation of a mechanism to exploit the temporal aspect of *dynamic, frequently changing* situations using RDF Stream Processing [16] technologies (RSP) in an HMAS platform
- (iii) The design and implementation of support for reasoning about *context-based conditions for access* to resources in an HMAS platform using SHACL Shapes [6]

To address space limitations of the current paper, example listings of RDF showing instances and implementation of various functionality aspects of our approach, based on a scenario discussed in Section 5, are made available in an online accessible Appendix¹.

2 Background and Related Work

To put our work into context, we need to provide an overview of the perspectives which it tries to bring together. Our contribution proposes an extension of HMAS platforms (specifically, those modeled in the Agents & Artifacts paradigm) with context management capabilities. To do so, it considers looking at artifacts as *prosumers* (provider and consumer) of context in a dynamic, streaming manner. Such a view enables the use of both static and dynamic information in the agent environment as the basis for conditioned access to resources in the HMAS. The following overview positions our work with respect to these aspects.

2.1 Hypermedia MAS

Ciortea et al. [15] introduce the guiding principles for Hypermedia MAS and furthermore provide one model for HMAS that abides by those principles, namely one of cognitive agents in *artifact*-based hypermedia environments. The model is based on the Agents & Artifacts (A&A) paradigm [25], which envisions the engineering of agent environment and of the interaction of agents *with their environment* by means of explicit resources (tools), generically called *artifacts*. The latter express *properties* (of themselves or of what they perceive in the environment), enable *actions* (on themselves or on the environment) and signal *events* (based on their internal state or of perceptions in the environment).

In the interpretation of [15], the artifact model resembles closely with the affordance model of the Web-of-Things ThingDescription specification [9], such that an alignment between artifact capabilities and Thing affordances (properties, actions, events) is envisioned for agent resources in an HMAS.

In follow-up work, the artefact representation in an HMAS is extended by means of signifiers [32], which are a means to *make agents aware* of all the ways in which they *could use* the affordances of an artefact, if they have a particular objective and some required capabilities. Signifiers inform agents of the conditions they need to fulfil, both in terms of internal capabilities, as well as their situation in the environment, which the authors of [32] call *the context* of an agent. A simple example of this would be conditions for *accessing* some action affordances of an artifact (e.g. an agent can *move* a robot arm if it can be authenticated, and if the robot arm is assigned to the same project as intended by the agent; the assistant agent of a user can *control* the smart lights of a hotel room, if the user is a hotel guest and physically present in the room).

¹ CASHMERE Online Appendix: <https://tinyurl.com/cashmere-eumas-online-appendix>

However, [32] does not currently provide a model for the *context* information referenced by an artifact signifier and it does not detail a principled way in which an artifact (or an agent) can come into the possession of this information within the HMAS in which it is deployed. Our work in CASHMERE addresses this concern, by showing: (i) how context can be represented such that it captures information content, as well as metadata about the information (e.g. how long is it valid, where was it generated), and (ii) how to manage information that can become *context* for other artifacts or agents in a mechanism that takes advantage of the infrastructure in an HMAS modeled after the A&A paradigm. In particular, the A&A view groups artifacts into a hierarchical set of *workspaces*, which enable a logical partitioning of resources. The information flow we propose exploits this setup to define preferred policies of information exchange, depending on *dimensions* (e.g. spatial distribution, organizational or activity centred considerations) of the engineered application.

2.2 Context Management and Stream Processing

Context information sharing in the IoT and WoT world has been actively studied from many perspectives [22]. Concerns regarding representation and provisioning of the information flow are often addressed by considering the application domain itself (e.g. smart environments, building automation, smart agriculture, smart manufacturing, security and privacy). It is important to note, however, that the HMAS paradigm envisions exploiting the web as a *global* interaction ground for agent-based applications, cutting across application domains with the set of design principles it proposes. Consequently, proposals for information representation and its flow have to be flexible enough to address several concerns (from modeling capability, to interoperability, to computational efficiency).

Stream Processing. An important aspect that needs to be addressed is how to properly manage and distinguish between information of different *update rates*: from information that is static, to information that concerns events or that has various degrees of temporal validity. Regarding the latter, the RDF Stream Processing (RSP) community [4] puts forth the vision of a web of data streams [17] whose key requirements capture many concerns that are relevant for context management in HMAS. The core element of the vision is the idea that content that is of interest to an actor should be *streamed* to them over the web, through a series of *web stream processors* (WeSP). While doing so, WeSPs need to balance between the distribution and scalability of operations (e.g. transformations, deductive or inductive reasoning) performed on both *stored* (more static) and *streamed* (dynamic) data, manage the variety of representation requirements (from simple key value items to timestamped RDF graphs) for data streams and provide meta information about the streams themselves. One key takeaway of [17] is that streams over the web need to have a clear management of producers and consumers of information, since default interaction over the web are stateless, such that polling techniques or other push-based mechanisms (e.g. WebSocket, MQTT) are needed for data streams. It is therefore a requirement to have a principled manner in which to (i) describe and know how and where

to access the content of streams, (ii) organize information of different update frequency levels in separate storing and processing pipelines that take into account the specifics of each, and (iii) ensure the required level of expressiveness depending on the usage of the streamed content.

These challenges give rise to new research on how to coordinate decentralized stream reasoners in an agent-like perspective [30]. In the CASHMERE framework we envision setting up the infrastructure for managing static and dynamic information at the level of a deployed HMAS platform. We exploit alignment of artifact / Thing event affordances with RDF streams, we introduce a service in an HMAS platform that explicitly indexes and manages static and dynamic (acting as "channels" into which streamed data can be sent while awaiting for consumers), and we leverage the HMAS *observability* and *single entry point* design principles to make discovery, self-description and access of streamed context data easy.

Context Representation. In terms of representing streamed data on the web [18], the RSP community has looked towards research in the area of RDF Stream Processing ([11, 20, 16]) and Streaming Linked Data [31]. One key identified aspect is that of addressing the variety of expressiveness requirements in terms of modeling *content* (different representation forms and RDF serialization methods) and its *annotations* (e.g. different notions of time - time instants, intervals, provenance) [14].

With respect to the expressiveness requirement, our own previous work (the CONSERT Meta-Model [29]) is an appropriate fit for a general method of context representation. CONSERT uses a reification-based view of information where *ContextAssertions* and *ContextAnnotations* are the main modeling elements. *ContextAssertions* use the predicate in a subject-predicate-object triple as the main model entity. A statement such as `locatedAt(agent_alex, lab308)` is modeled as a binary *ContextAssertion*, whereby the central element is the fact of being `locatedAt` and the subject and object entities are `agent_alex` and `lab308`. However, *ContextAssertions* can have an n-ary form with a predicate and several role entities, lending itself useful for self-contained representations of several pieces of information (e.g. the reception of a shopping order with a delivery address, delivery deadline, selected items). *ContextAnnotations* describe *ContextAssertions* further, adding meta information such as timestamp of registration, interval of validity, provenance of the assertion.

Importantly, *ContextAssertions* are characterized by a *mode of acquisition*, an operational attribute signaling how *dynamic* the assertion is. *Static ContextAssertions* refer to information that holds true indefinitely (e.g. the spatial containment of a room in a building). *Profiled ContextAssertions* have a long-term, but still limited temporal validity (e.g. the employment status of a researcher), while *dynamic ContextAssertions* refer to event-like information which is assumed to change frequently in a system (e.g. the physical location of a person in a building).

The modeling elements of CONSERT make *ContextAssertions* a suitable information *exchange* format, usable when communicating context information along

streams, between artifacts and agents. The CONSERT Meta-Model has a realization in the form of the CONSERT Ontology². To promote flexibility, however, under the CASHMERE framework for HMAS, artifact information is converted to a CONSERT based representation *only* when it needs to be streamed, so as to take advantage of operational aspects that differentiate between processing of static/profiled versus dynamic information. In Section 3.1 we indicate a mechanism for on-demand conversion between typical ontology-based information representation to a CONSERT-based modeling.

2.3 Attribute-Based Access Control

Recent surveys highlight that in *dynamic* and *open* computing environments, such as IoT and WoT, traditional access control models such as Role-Based Access Control (RBAC) are not adapted to fit application dynamics [24]. Considering the discussion in previous sections, access to artifacts in HMAS platforms is strongly benefited from employing an Attribute-Based Access Control (ABAC), which proposes that subject requests to perform operations on a resource are granted or denied based on *attributes* of the subjects, resources and the environment, and the policies that relate to these attributes [26].

While the access control mechanism that we are proposing under CASHMERE does not deviate from existing formalization applied in web services or the IoT domain [19, 12], it is novel in its operationalization at the level of an HMAS, as well as in the leveraged technology stack. Specifically, we propose use of an access control modeling and policy management model that is guided by the Web-Access Control [8] specifications of SOLID [7]. We make use of the hierarchy of logical inclusion containers (workspaces) that are available in an HMAS that follows the A&A paradigm to define policy resolution methods. We further leverage both static and dynamic context information reasoning, using SHACL [6] and RDF Stream Reasoning in C-SPARQL [11] to construct the access conditions. Our proposal is particularly similar to [33], which uses RDF, SHACL, WebIDs [10] and nanopublications over Linked Data to develop pattern based access control for multi-stakeholder shared work projects. Unlike [33], CASHMERE addresses a broader class of applications, facilitated by HMAS, seeking to align with and use the hierarchical representation in platforms such as Ygdrasil [15].

3 Context Management in an HMAS Platform

The proposal to extract *streams* of context information from agents and artifacts in an HMAS carries with it the additional requirement of servicing web protocols that enable a continuous connection between the producer and consumer of a context stream. The HMAS design principles do not impose capabilities on the physical machines that host resources (e.g. artifacts that reflect

² CONSERT Core and Annotation ontology modules: <https://tinyurl.com/consert-ontology>

physical devices, web services) of an HMAS. Given these considerations, in the CASHMERE framework we consider it necessary to extend the functionality of a deployed HMAS platform with a dedicated *ContextManagementService*, as shown in Figure 1. An HMAS representation using the HMAS Ontology [3] starts

Fig. 1. Proposed extension under CASHMERE of an HMAS representation with services for Context Management and the access control it enables.

from its *Hypermedia MASPlatform* definition which can host several *Workspaces*. The latter can recursively contain other *Workspaces* or *Artifact* instances which implement functionality available in the agent environment. CASHMERE proposes a first extension of an HMAS representation (see the blue items in Figure 1) by introducing the representation for a platform-level hosted service called *cashmere:ContextManagementService*. The latter is responsible with context information provisioning at the level of the whole platform and it has three main responsibilities: (i) managing context information streams, (ii) managing repositories of *profiled* or *static* context information that is to be shared at the level of the platform, and (iii) managing a set of logical, frequently exploited *situation boundaries*, called *ContextDomains*. We detail each of these responsibilities in what follows.

3.1 Context Streams

The artifacts that are deployed in an HMAS have their functionality extended themselves, shown in Figure 2, where grey lines indicate functional aspects. An artifact developer can opt to turn an *event* affordance into the source of a *context stream*. In such case, the event information will be converted into a *ContextAssertion* representation, that has mandatory *ContextAnnotations* for: (i) a logical timestamp, and (ii) the provenance of the event (the URI of the deployed artifact). Similarly, artifact *property* affordances can be shared as *static* or *profiled ContextAssertions*, that are made available in corresponding RDF Graphs. Properties that are exposed as *profiled ContextAssertions* can be given additional *ContextAnnotations*, most relevantly a duration of validity.

Notice that the instance URIs shown in Figures 1 and 2 (relating to the example scenario from Section 5) follow the single entry point principle in HMAS,

having a path that enables easy navigation from the platform level and automatic reference determination, if key elements are known. For example, URIs *ContextStreams* managed at both artifact and platform level are obtained by appending the word "Stream" to the local name of the *ContextAssertion* whose instances are being streamed (e.g. *ex:LocatedAt*, *ex:BatteryStatus*) and concatenating the result to the default stream path $\langle hmas_root \rangle / ctxmgmt / context / dynamic$ for platforms, $\langle hmas_root \rangle / workspaces / \langle wsp_id \rangle / artifacts / \langle art_id \rangle / context / dynamic$ for artifacts).

Fig. 2. Proposed extension under CASHMERE of an Artifact representation and functionality. Artifact events can be sent through context streams and their properties can be exposed as *static* or *profiled* context information.

Note that populating the static and profiled, as well as the context stream, with information is an *on-demand* process, meaning that updates are driven by consumer interest. Figuring out appropriate caching and demand prediction policies at the level of individual artifacts is an aspect currently left for future work. The on-demand working mode adds little overhead to current artifact design, since it only complements *the representation* of information already generated by the artifact, such that it can be readily shared with other parties in a standardized manner. This approach follows the flexibility principle for taming variety of data in stream processors [14] and proposes addressing it through semantic web technologies that make conversion of data representation a manageable task. Technology stacks such as RDF Mapping Language (RML [5]) or the SPARQL Rules feature from SHACL [6]. Once converted to an *ContextAssertion* form, streaming of corresponding RDF content in a manner compatible with existing RDF stream reasoners, such as those outlined in Section 2.2 can be enabled through frameworks such as TripleWave [23]. In Listing 3.1 of the online Appendix we give an example of using SHACL SPARQL Rules to transform an artifact event (e.g. the presence of a user in a university room) expressed in a given domain ontology into a *dynamic ContextAssertion*.

With respect to context streams, another important extension is at the level of the HMAS platform itself. The *ContextManagement Service* (see Figure 1) is responsible for maintaining a record of context streams that are managed by artifacts deployed on the platform or by the platform itself, in case that context information is required from services on the web outside of those deployed on the platform. The registry maintained at platform level follows a predictable URI path ($\langle hmas_root \rangle / ctxmgmt / context / dynamic$) respecting the single entry point principle, as well as the requirement in [14] to have a meta-description of the

stream itself. Notably, accessing the `<hmas_root>/ctxmgmt/context/dynamic` URI produces a representation of managed `cashmere:ContextStream` instances that indicate the type of `ContextAssertions` that are exchanged over the stream, the mode of update (e.g. periodic or on-change) and the producer of the stream (the artifact URI or the URI of the external service providing the stream).

3.2 Static and Profiled Context

In both Figures 1 and 2 one can observe the presence of managed RDF context graphs that are divided between *static* and *profiled* information. In both cases, these graphs hold information that an HMAS platform or any individual artifact wants to *share* freely. This means that consumers (agents or other resources) accessing the information will not have any restriction on accessing the shared context information, apart from obtaining knowledge about the endpoint to the HMAS platform (according to the single endpoint principle of HMAS design).

The RDF Graphs at the platform level have a double functionality. If an artifact developer chooses to host RDF graphs of static or profiled `ContextAssertions` at the level of the artifact, then the platform level equivalents will contain a reference to the graph hosted at the level of the artifact together with a mention of the *type* of `ContextAssertion` instances that are accessible there. If, however, artifact-level hosting or on-demand generation of *static* and *profiled* context contents is impractical (e.g. due to low computational resource on the host machine of the artifact), then an artifact developer can choose to submit *static* or *profiled* context information when the artifact is first deployed at HMAS platform level. Since *profiled* context information is considered to have seldom updates (e.g. when the validity interval expires) the effort to employ mechanisms, such as those outlined in Section 3.1, to convert from a domain vocabulary to the `ContextAssertion` representation will be minimal.

Information registered at platform-level *static* and *profiled* context graphs is stored in a *Named* RDF Graph form, whereby the URI of the artifact or resource that has provided the information is used as the graph *name*.

3.3 ContextDomains and ContextDomain Groups

In Figure 1, the `ContextManagement Service` of an HMAS platform is shown to manage instances of `cashmere:ContextDomains`, which in turn give rise to `cashmere:ContextDomainGroups`. The notion of a `ContextDomain` was originally introduced in prior work [28] and relates to a logical partitioning of context-informed *situations*, where a particular provisioning of context information imposes itself. For example, context information can be managed and provisioned with priority depending on cases where actors share the same physical space (e.g. a university room, a manufacturing workspace), are engaged in the same activity (e.g. a lecture, a manufacturing process) or who are part of the same organization (e.g. a university, a company, a research lab).

`ContextDomains` were originally modeled to be the object instances of binary

ContextAssertion that represented so called *ContextDimensions* (e.g. *locatedIn(Person, UniversitySpace)*, *engagedIn(Agent, ManufacturingProcess)*, *memberOf(Researcher, University)*). The concept was expanded in more recent work [27] to refer to, possibly more complex, *situation definitions* that would be frequently leveraged in applications. For example, our reference scenario (see Section 5) describes authorizing access to affordances of a smart light artifact, under condition that the accessing agent is physically present in the same room as that with the smart light and that it represents a user who is employed by the university owning the device. Importantly, our previous work [27] designs a reasoning mechanism which enables specifying the conditions (based on context information) which *count-as* relevant for different actors (agents or resources) to be seen as being part of a situation that is labeled as a *ContextDomain*. In the CASHMERE framework, the set of actors in an HMAS that are part of the same *contextual situation* are defined as *members* of the corresponding *ContextDomainGroup*. In Figure 1, the *ContextDomain* identified by the <http://example.com/upb-hmas/ctxmgmt/domains/lab308domain> URI refers to researchers physically present in Lab308 of the university building. The figure also shows the URI scheme that connects a *ContextDomain* to its *ContextDomainGroup* and to the RDF Graph of statements of membership within the group.

An example of the reasoning mechanism used to grant or revoke membership within the above mentioned *ContextDomainGroup* is given in Listing 1.3 of the online Appendix. It is based on the C-SPARQL 2.0 [11] RDF stream processing engine and the main advantage of the approach is that it can leverage the temporal aspect of dynamic context information. Notably, the semantics of stream operators that we use is based on triggering when the content of the underlying stream *changes* from one *window* of processing to the next (this corresponds to ISTREAM and DSTREAM operators in the RSP-QL specification [16]). In this manner, two queries, one using an ISTREAM and one using a DSTREAM operator, under the same conditions of verification, will produce statements that grant (ISTREAM) and revoke (DSTREAM) a membership in a *ContextDomainGroup*. Generated membership statements are stored in an RDF Graph that has *named graph* sections corresponding to each *ContextDomain* (see the example of the `<hmas_root>/ctxmgmt/domains/lab308domain/group/memberships` RDF membership graph in Figure 1). This enables quick and controlled access to a *data graph* of current memberships in each *ContextDomain*, that would need to be validated against a *shapes* graph by means of a SHACL processor that verifies membership, as showcased in Section 4.

Since a *ContextDomain* acts as an element of defining situations, it and the set of count-as membership conditions for agents and resources in an HMAS have to be added by HMAS developers, either on deploy time, or on throughout the lifecycle of an HMAS platform (e.g. when new workspaces are defined or new artifacts are deployed). As in previously discussed cases, the principle of single-entry point applies for the discovery of *ContextDomains*. When accessing the representation of a *ContextDomain* in an HMAS, details about the C-SPARQL based rule that regulates membership in the domain are also given, such that

an agent can interpret the context which it needs to share (expressed in terms of *ContextAssertions*) to be considered a member of the *ContextDomain*.

4 Dynamic Access Control with CASHMERE

A relevant use of the proposed context management framework at the level of an A&A-based HMAS framework is that of authorized access to resources. Methods for a token based, *authenticated* access can already be readily used, since artifacts in an A&A HMAS closely align with Things in the W3C ThingDescription specification [9] (as is the case of the Yggdrasil platform [15]), which define methods for authenticated access. However, as argued in the Introduction, dynamics of interactions in an HMAS require a dynamic method of *authorization*.

Notice in Figure 1 that CASHMERE proposes the extension of an HMAS representation with another additional perspective, which leverages context information, by declaring *Workspace* and *Artifact* instances as having the additional *cashmere:ContextAuthorizedResource* type. The working principles of the context-based authorization process were introduced in previous work [27] and in the current proposal we are expanding the approach and redesigning the involved technology stack.

Fig. 3. Diagram showing the principal concepts from the CASHMERE Ontology which help define a context authorized resource in an HMAS.

The discussion of the proposed approach starts from the building blocks shown in Figure 3. The CASHMERE Ontology defines the concept of a *ContextAuthorizedResource*, which enables HMAS designers to declare the access to *Workspaces* and *Artifacts* as guarded by a *ContextBasedAuthorization*. The latter is as a subclass of an ACL Authorization (see the ACL Ontology [1] from SOLID [7]) and therefore provides the option to set read and write/append access modes to the affordances of the resource. The *ContextBasedAuthorization* declares its conditions using a *cashmere:ContextBasedAccessCondition* class instance. The latter declares a target entity for the access conditions (in our case, an instance

of a *foaf:Agent*), generically identified by *cashmere:accessRequester*, but dynamically swapped out at runtime for the WebID of the agent making the request. The root access condition declares a conjunction of specific context-based conditions (which are SHACL Node Shapes) using the *cashmere:containsConditions* property. These conditions need to match the interaction situation of the requesting agent (see Listing 2.1 in the online Appendix). The SHACL Shape class for the specific conditions depends on the *type* of context information that is referenced (CONSERV context acquisition types discussed in Section 2.2). For dynamic context, the *ContextDomain* membership condition discussed in Section 3.3 is used, while for *profiled* (i.e. *ContextAssertions* with annotations) and *static* context the *Profiled-* and *StaticContextCondition* Shapes are used respectively (see also Listing 2.2 in the online Appendix). A particularity of the latter two is that they can directly reference the RDF Named Graph(s) that will act as data graphs for the SHACL shape validation. The *contextGraphURI* data property is used to specify the set of artifact-level RDF Named Graphs that compose the *data graphs* against which the SHACL shapes will be validated. If the property is left unspecified, the validation data graphs are obtained based on the default platform-level *static* and *profiled* RDF Named Graphs (see Figure 1).

Fig. 4. Sequence of interactions and internal processing steps to authorize access to an HMAS agent to a desired *Artifact*.

The sequence diagram detailing the interaction between an HMAS agent and a desired *Artifact* is shown in Figure 4. If an *Artifact* or *any Workspace* along a transitive containment closure is declared as a *ContextAuthorizedResource*, then access to its affordances is mediated by the HMAS platform through the *Context ManagementService* (step 3). The first thing is to determine the *effective* Authorization. This procedure follows the recommended specification in the SOLID WAC protocol [8], whereby if an *ACL Resource* is not explicitly declared for the

initially requested web resource, then the search for an authorization declaration is deferred to looking for one in the *container* of the currently considered web resource. Since hypermedia MAS are naturally structured along *Workspace* containment hierarchies, the *hmas:contains* relation (see Figure 1) is used by the *ContextManagementService* to determine the *effective ContextBasedAuthorization* instance. Once the authorization requirements are obtained, execution is passed to a *ContextValidationService*, whose task it is to unpack the top-level *ContextBasedAccessCondition* into individual *dynamic* (*ContextDomain* membership based), profiled or static access conditions expressed by their corresponding SHACL *NodeShapes* (steps 4 and 5 in Figure 4). The principal task is then to identify the URL of the corresponding RDF context graph required to validate the SHACL shape and forward the validation call to the resource in the HMAS managing that graph. For a dynamic, *ContextDomain* membership condition, the call is forwarded to the *ContextManagement* Service, specifically, the section of it managing the membership RDF graph for the *ContextDomainGroup* defined by the required *ContextDomain* (step 6a). Validation of static or profiled context access conditions (steps 6b and 6c) depends on the given *cashmere:contextGraphURI* (see Figure 3). If none are present, the *ContextManagement Service* will use its default static and profiled RDF context graphs as data graphs for SHACL shape validation. If declarations are present, the *ContextManagement Service* uses its context graphs as indexes to determine the resource in the HMAS platform which manages the declared context graphs and forwards the validation request to it.

In our example scenario (see Section 5 and Listings 2.1 - 2.3 from the online Appendix), access to the *light308* is predicated on membership in the *lab308domain* group and on the profiled context information of the employment status of the person on whose behalf the request is made. The *lab308domain* membership is determined using the C-SPARQL query from Listing 1.3 in the online Appendix, which uses the stream of dynamic *ex:LocatedAt ContextAssertions* to determine physical presence of the requesting agent in Lab308 over the past 5 minutes. Since the university is a trusted entity and it owns both the smart light and the HMAS platform instance that manages it, the *profiled* employment information is made available in the default *profiled* RDF graph of the *ContextManagement Service* for the UPB HMAS (see Listing 1.2 in the online Appendix). In Listing 2.2 from the online Appendix, the *cashmere:ProfiledContextCondition* instance showcases use of *TemporalValidity* annotations for the provided *ex:WorksAt* profiled *ContextAssertion*.

5 Development and Discussion

Scenario. To drive development and evaluation of the proposed CASHMERE extension to HMAS platforms, the following simple scenario is presented. A university manages a smart campus, wherein different web-enabled devices are present (e.g. smart light, smart blinds). The university encourages each lab to be individually responsible for the smart devices it installs in their room, as long

as they are made available in the HMAS platform of the university (*ex:upb_hmas* in the Listings). Researchers from Lab308 desire to use the smart light in their lab (*ex:light308* in the Listings) to implement a visual notification service for various meeting and teaching events. However, university policy maintains that use of affordances from any smart device on campus be restricted to employed personnel who are physically present in the rooms where the device resides (thus preventing university visitors from interacting with the devices, as well as any kind of remote control). Though simple, the scenario easily introduces the need for context-based authorized access to the smart light, which conditions agents on a profiled context (the employment status of their user) and a dynamic one (the stream of physical presence information of agent users).

Development The presented scenario has been implemented at a proof-of-concept level, with a focus on leveraging context information to provide the dynamic access control discussed in Section 4. We created the CASHMERE Ontology³ to provide the vocabulary that supports the extensions to an HMAS platform (see Figure 1, as well as the terminology used to describe context-based authorizations (see Figure 3). We further created a fork of the Yggdrasil HMAS platform⁴ which we extended with several aspects. Access to artifact affordances is now mediated by the SHACL Shape based context conditioning representation used to specify authorization requirements. The interactions between an agent and a desired artifact show in Figure 4 are supported by a new Context Management Service and a Web Access Control Service that run at the level of an Yggdrasil platform. In particular, the Context Management Service implements an RSP reasoner based on C-SPARQL to infer membership in configured *ContextDomain Groups* (*lab308Domain* in our reference scenario).

The current demo stage has some limitations with respect to the overall design presented in Section 3. Specifically, it currently supports only platform level *static* and *profiled* context graphs. Further, the context streams (e.g. the *LocatedAt* dynamic *ContextAssertion* stream) are deployed locally, on platform setup, to be able to quickly iterate on testing and adjustments of stream update policies (e.g. frequency of new location updates). Scaling to the complete design is scheduled in near-term future work.

Discussion The presented integration of context management capabilities into HMAS platforms leverages an intersection of visions from two communities (WebAgents [2] and RSP [4]), as well as an opportunistic fit between the functionalities of core elements of design (e.g. artifacts in HMAS and stream processors in RSP) and the technology stack developed in each community. In contrast to many other context information sharing frameworks for IoT or WoT [22], CASHMERE puts the context of *agents* interacting in their HMAS environment as the focus of the provisioning. It enables the use of context to condition access, but also to *recommend* artifact or service affordances to agents, depending on the situation. Different from other frameworks, CASHMERE introduces an explicit, RSP-based method to define *situation labels* (*ContextDomain* memberships). A

³ CASHMERE Ontology: <http://tinyurl.com/cashmere-ont>

⁴ CASHMERE Fork of Yggdrasil: <https://github.com/aimas-upb/yggdrasil>

shared ContextDomain can explicitly indicate the set of entities (agents and artifacts in the HMAS) that *should* subscribe to each other’s context streams. The engineering principles of *ContextDomains* also enable a higher degree of flexibility and reuse, than that found in other approaches. Large scale and open HMAS applications bring about several situations that require repeated leveraging of the same kind of context to inform desired functionality. Moreover, complex, time varying situations can benefit from a breakdown of a subset of conditions into *ContextDomain* membership requirements, that can be composed bottom up, as opposed to having to rewrite the full conditioning for each new situation.

In terms of the architectural models discussed in [22], CASHMERE is in the adaptive category (both cloud-based, as well as local edge), since it integrates with A&A HMAS design principles, which enable this versatility. Furthermore, all the introduced building functionalities adhere to *web-based* processing. At representation level, the CONCERT Meta Model is on par with the most expressive representation methods surveyed in [22], given the existence of n-ary *Context-Assertions* and mechanisms to convert on-demand from simple RDF triplets to the CONCERT model. The extension of HMAS working principles with on-demand RDF Graph streaming for context provisioning means that more comprehensive descriptions of a situation can be transmitted per stream item. Moreover, CONCERT offers the capability to specify meta-information and properties that can inform operational aspects (the mode of acquisition of context).

Regarding context-based access control, we first note that it is just one potential use for context managed at the level of an HMAS. Methods for artifact affordance discovery such as the Signifier Exposure Mechanism [32] discussed in Section 2.1 can readily benefit from the same infrastructure, not to condition, but to advertise / suggest. The proposed mechanism for access validation brings no additional overhead, when compared to the typical web-based access control functionality as envisioned by SOLID [7]. We take SOLID WAC [8] as a reference since it has a natural fit for web resources (which is the case for HMAS), as opposed to application-centric ABAC systems that cannot scale as easily over a distributed set of resources.

In terms of limitations, the main contention point in the designed context provisioning will be in the speed of SHACL validation and execution of streaming SPARQL queries, depending on the volume of streamed context, as well as in the size of the RDF Named Graphs that hold static, profiled or dynamic *ContextDomain* membership information. Evaluation of these impacts and research on mitigation strategies is an aspect of future work.

6 Conclusion and Future Work

The CASHMERE framework proposes a principled approach to extend HMAS platforms that follow the A&A paradigm with the ability to manage context information that can be leveraged in multiple ways, from context-based conditioning of access to resources in an HMAS, to the characterization of situations in which resource affordances should be advertised (signaled) to agents for use in

their goals. The proposed extension carefully follows the design guidelines from HMAS and RDF Stream Processing to develop an on-demand context provisioning mechanism, that uses a semantic-web based technology stack (e.g. ontologies, SHACL, RSP, SOLID WAC). Choice of the CONSERT Meta-Model for context representation covers requirements of expressive modeling, temporal validity annotations and operational support (in terms of context update modes).

Future work includes development of a full-scale demonstrator of the context management and access control functionality described in Sections 3 and 4, based on the scenario which was outlined in Section 5 and which will be implemented in full on university premises. Longer term objectives aim at addressing the load processing evaluation and the limitations identified in the discussion from Section 5.

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